

DIVERSE VIEWPOINTS OF WOMEN CHARACTERS OF THE NOVEL “PRIDE AND PREJUDICE” BY JANE AUSTEN

Ikramova Kamola Shukhratovna

Scientific researcher of Samarkand state institute of Foreign languages,

kamolaikramova471@gmail.com

Abstract: Jane Austen's novel "Pride and Prejudice" (1813) examines the challenges faced by women in the 19th century, particularly in terms of marriage. She delves into the societal expectations placed upon women and the limited options available to them. The novel's main character defies societal expectations by thinking and acting independently. During this time, women had limited options, often restricted to marriage or becoming governesses if they were educated. Family pressures often influenced women's futures, pushing them to find husbands who could support them financially. Elizabeth, the main character, is unique in her independence and unconventional nature, ultimately marrying for love. This research article aims to explore the viewpoints of women in Jane Austen's novel "Pride and Prejudice" by examining the personalities of each female character.

Key words: Pride And Prejudice, Persuasion, Women Characters, Representation, Marriage, Love.

Annotatsiya: Jeyn Ostinning "G'urur va Andisha" (1813) romani XIX asrda ayollar hayoti davomida duch kelgan qiyinchiliklarni, ayniqsa nikoh bilan bog'liq muammolarni yoritib bergan. Ushbu asarda, ayollar zimmasiga yuklangan jamiyat talablarini va ular uchun mavjud bo'lgan cheklangan imkoniyatlarni chuqur tahlil qiladi. Asosiy qahramon jamiyat talablariga qarshi chiqib, mustaqil fikrlash va harakat qilish orqali o'ziga xosligini namoyon etadi. O'sha davrda ayollar ko'pincha nikoh yoki, agar ular o'qimishli bo'lsa, guvernantalik bilan cheklanib qolgan edi. Oila bosimlari ko'pincha ayollarning kelajagini shakllantirib, ularni moliyaviy jihatdan qo'llab-quvvatlay oladigan turmush o'rtoq izlashga undardi. Asosiy qahramon Elizabet o'zining mustaqilligi va o'ziga xos tabiati bilan ajralib turadi va oxir-oqibat

muhabbat tufayli turmushga chiqadi. Ushbu ilmiy maqolada, Jeyn Ostinning "G'urur va Andisha" asaridagi ayollarning turli xil dunyoqarashlari har bir ayol qahramonning shaxsiyatini tahlil qilish orqali o'rganishni maqsad qilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: g'urur, andisha, ayol qahramonlar, tasvirlash, nikoh, sevgi.

Jane Austen, a British author, was famous for her novels written during the Regency period. Her most recognized work, "Pride and Prejudice," published in 1813, follows the story of Elizabeth Bennet, the second of five daughters in the Bennet family. This scientific article will analyze how the female characters in "Pride and Prejudice" represent societal expectations and norms during the Regency era. It will delve into the personalities and social circumstances of key characters like Elizabeth, Mrs. Bennet, Jane Bennet, Lydia, and Kitty. This article will examine how the characters' actions and decisions are influenced by their social standing and views on society. It is important to note that "Pride and Prejudice" is actually set in the early 19th century during the Regency era, not the Victorian era. Although a woman was in power as the monarch, women in the 19th century had limited opportunities and were often viewed as perfect, innocent figures without legal rights. This article highlights the role of women in the 19th century by analyzing the various characters in the novel. The novel focuses on the Bennet sisters, especially Elizabeth, the protagonist, and their middle-class family. Because Mr. Bennet has no sons, the family's property is entailed, meaning it can only be inherited by a male relative. In this situation, Mr. Bennet's distant cousin, Mr. Collins, is expected to inherit the estate. This worries Mrs. Bennet about her daughters' financial future after their father's death, as they would depend on Mr. Collins' kindness. Elizabeth's mother, Mrs. Bennet, is entirely focused on securing husbands for her daughters: "The business of her life was to get her daughters married; its solace was visiting and news" (*Pride and Prejudice*, p. 5). As a loving mother, she wants the best for them, which leads her to pressure Mr. Bennet to introduce their daughters to Mr. Bingley, a wealthy and unmarried young man who has just moved into the area: "If I can but see one of my daughters happily settled at Netherfield and all the others equally well married, I shall have nothing to

wish for" (*Pride and Prejudice*, p. 9). However, her motherly love is sometimes overshadowed by her ambition for their marriages. For example, she sends Jane to visit Mr. Bingley on horseback, knowing it will rain, hoping Jane will have to stay at Netherfield. When Jane falls ill, Mrs. Bennet isn't too concerned; feeling satisfied that this gives her daughter more time near Mr. Bingley. Mrs. Bennet also enjoys gossiping and frequently behaves inappropriately in social settings. She is depicted as lacking intelligence and having limited knowledge and a volatile personality. "She was a woman of mean understanding; little information and uncertain temper" (*Pride and Prejudice*, p. 5). Mrs. Bennet often blurts out her thoughts at the wrong moments, like when she excitedly talks about Jane's possible marriage to Mr. Bingley with Lady Lucas in a public room. : "It was an animating subject and Mrs. Bennet seemed incapable of fatigue while enumerating the advantages of the match" (*Pride and Prejudice*, p. 111). Mrs. Bennet fails to realize that her behavior impacts her daughters' prospects. Her indiscreet conversation with Lady Lucas leads to Mr. Bingley being distanced from Jane, as Mr. Darcy and Mr. Bingley's sisters remark that "with such a father and mother, and such low connections" (*Pride and Prejudice*, p. 40). The Bennet sisters have limited prospects of finding good husbands. This emphasizes how a woman's future is greatly influenced by her family's standing and social relationships, with marriage being the primary means of achieving financial security. Elizabeth Bennet, also known as Lizzy, is the second-oldest of the Bennet sisters and is twenty years old. She is characterized by her "lively, playful disposition which delighted in anything ridiculous" (*Pride and Prejudice*, p. 12). Elizabeth Bennet's keen observations and intelligence have made her a very famous and memorable character in literature. "For the first time in English literature, outside Shakespeare, we meet heroines who are credible, with minds, with the capacity to think for themselves, with ambition and wit" (qtd. in "Study Guide for *Pride and Prejudice* by Jane Austen," p. 10). Lizzy is Mr. Bennet's favorite daughter. When describing his daughters, he remarks that "they are all silly and ignorant like other girls; but Lizzy has something more of quickness than her sisters" (*Pride and Prejudice*, p. 5).

Conclusion: Austen's portrayal of women in *Pride and Prejudice* highlights the various ways they dealt with societal expectations related to marriage, class, and personal freedom. Through characters like Elizabeth and Charlotte, she examines the restricted options available to women and presents different viewpoints on how they could exercise their independence within those limitations. The novel serves as a nuanced exploration of gender roles and women's autonomy in Austen's era. Women were primarily expected to adhere to societal norms, particularly regarding marriage and proper social conduct. Characters like Mrs. Bennet illustrate the pressure to arrange favorable marriages for daughters, showing how women's futures were often dependent on their marital success. However, Austen subtly critiques these expectations through Elizabeth Bennet, who prioritizes intelligence, independence, and personal values over wealth or social standing in a partner. Austen also introduces characters like Charlotte Lucas, who marries for practical reasons, and Lady Catherine, who exerts power but is constrained by her class. Through this range of female characters, Austen exposes both the restrictions imposed on women and their different ways of responding to societal expectations.

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